

Synthesis of some novel 4-substituted coumarins having antibacterial activity (Part-I)

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Methyl coumarin-4-methyl acetate on bromination in dioxane or dichloroethane as solvent resulted in sidechain bromination giving α -bromo derivative. The same reaction when carried out in acetic acid resulted in selective synthesis of 3-bromo derivatives. The α -bromo derivatives on reaction with various urea derivatives give novel nitrogen heterocycles (imidazolones) substituted at 4-position of coumarin ring. The α -bromo derivatives when reacted with various 1,2-diamino compounds yielded fused 2-pyrazinones attached at 4-position of coumarin ring. Considering the potential biological activities of other 4-substituted coumarins and biological importance of imidazoles, pyrazines, triazines and oxazines in drug synthesis, the new heterocycles were examined for antibacterial properties and have shown positive results.

In continuation with our work on the synthesis of 4-substituted coumarins¹, we present herein the novel route for the synthesis of some new heterocycles substituted at the 4-position of coumarin ring.

In this paper we present the bromination of methyl substituted coumarin 4-methyl acetates, using dioxane dibromide² as a reagent for bromination in dioxane and using bromine in dichloroethane as a solvent at room temperature.

Results and discussion

The α -bromo derivatives react with one amino group of the diamino compound such as *o*-phenylenediamine (**8**), 2,3-diamino uracil (**9**) forming amide, which subsequently undergo cyclization in presence of base to form benzopyrazinone derivatives. The cyclization of α -bromo derivatives with urea and thiourea, were carried out in presence of the base such as pyridine or triethyl amine forming imidazolone derivatives (**6,7**).

When reacted with thiosemicarbazide (**10**) it yielded 1,2,4-triazine derivatives in the presence of the base e.g. dry K₂CO₃ or triethylamine. 4-Amino-3-thio-1,2,4-triazin was reacted with α -bromocoumarin 4-methyl acetate in isopropyl alcohol using base like triethyl amine or dry K₂CO₃ to give tetrazinone derivatives (**11**) (thiadiazine ring fused to 1,2,4-triazine).

Reaction with 2-aminophenol gave amide derivative which undergoes cyclization on treatment with base like triethylamine to yield benzoxazine derivatives substituted at 4-position of coumarins (**12**). However desired product

could not be isolated from the reaction of α -bromonaphthopyran-2-one-4-methyl acetate (derived from β -naphthol), with 2-aminophenol due to too many impurities formed during the reactions.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Spectrometer (200 MHz) with TMS as internal reference. The IR spectra were recorded on FTIR spectrometer with KBr pellets.

Synthesis of coumarin-4-acetic acid (2) :

Citric acid (96 g, 0.5 mol) was heated with concentrated H₂SO₄ (160 ml) at 60–65° with constant stirring avoiding excess foaming. To the acetonedicarboxylic acid in concentrated H₂SO₄ was added the cresols or xylenols or naphthols (**1**) (0.51 mol) under vigorous stirring at 0–5° over a period of 1–1.5 h. Stirring was continued at 5° for 2 h. Reaction mixture was then allowed to stand for 24 h at 30°. The solution was then poured in ice and water. The product precipitated was filtered. The crude product was purified by dissolving in NaHCO₃ solution followed by clarification with activated charcoal and filtration. Filtrate was acidified with conc. HCl to give respective coumarin-4-acetic acids (**2**).

Synthesis of coumarin 4-acetate (3) :

Intimate mixture of coumarin-4-acetic acid (0.1 mol) and alcohol (75 ml) was refluxed in presence of catalytic amount of concentrated sulfuric acid for 5–6 h. Reaction mixture was cooled to 15–20° when coumarin-4-acetates

(3) crystallized out. The product was filtered and treated with dilute NaHCO₃ solution. The crystals of coumarin-4-acetates were then washed thoroughly with water and dried.

Synthesis of 3-bromo coumarin 4-methyl acetate (4) :

To the solution of coumarin-4-acetate (4.3 mmol) in dry acetic acid (10 ml) at 25°, was added a solution of Br₂ (5.5 mmol) in acetic acid (5 ml) over 30 min. Reaction mixture was stirred at 30° for 8 h. Reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion, the reaction mixture was drowned in ice-cold solution of 3–4% sodium thiosulfate in water. The precipitated solids were stirred for 30 min. Product was filtered and washed well with water and dried to get the crude product. The crude solids were crystallized from 90% ethanol to get pure solids of 3-bromo coumarin-4-acetate (4). The yields, melting points and spectral data of the various 3-bromo coumarin-4-methyl acetate are as follows. **4a** yield 75%, m.p. 170–171°; δ_{H} 2.53 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.83 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 4.21 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.22–7.36 (2H, m, C5H + C7H), 7.53–7.57 (1H, d, C8H); ν_{max} 1732 (C=O of lactone), 1682 (C=O of ester), 725 (C-Br); **4b** yield 71%, m.p. 164–165°; δ_{H} 2.45 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.73 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 4.12 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.12–7.26 (2H, m, C5H + C8H), 7.43–7.47 (1H, d, C6H); ν_{max} 1727 (C=O of lactone), 1620 (C=O of ester), 739 (C-Br); **4c** yield 90%, m.p. 193–195°; δ_{H} 2.35 (6H, 2s, 2CH₃), 3.74 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 4.11 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.15 (1H, s, C5H), 7.28 (1H, s, C8H); ν_{max} 1729 (C=O of lactone), 1679 (C=O of ester), 695 (C-Br); **4d** yield 80%, m.p. 124–125°; δ_{H} 2.39 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.44 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.74 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 4.12 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.17 (1H, s, C5H), 7.26 (1H, s, C7H); ν_{max} 1735 (C=O of lactone), 1682 (C=O of ester), 689 (C-Br); **4e** yield 77%, m.p. 183–185°; δ_{H} 2.42 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.48 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.74 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 4.13 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.13 (1H, s, C6H), 7.20 (1H, s, C8H); ν_{max} 1742 (C=O of lactone), 1692 (C=O of ester), 746 (C-Br).

Synthesis of coumarin-4- α -bromo methyl acetate (5) :

To the solution of coumarin-4-methyl acetate (3) (4.3 mmol) in dry dioxane (40 ml) at 25°, was added the solution of Br₂ (1.0 g, 6.25 mmol) in dioxane (10 ml) over 30 min. The reaction mixture was stirred at 30° for 10–12 h. When the starting compound was consumed completely, (TLC monitoring) the reaction mixture was then drowned in ice-cold solution of 3–4% sodium thiosulfate. The precipitated solids were stirred for 30 min, filtered and washed well with water and dried to get the crude product. The crude solids were crystallized from methanol to get pure coumarin-4- α -bromo methyl acetate (5).

In case of 6-methyl coumarin-4-methyl acetate bromination in dioxane yielded mixture of both 3- and α -bromo

derivatives. Selectivity for α -bromo derivative was achieved when dichloroethane was used as solvent. In case of **5c** and **5f** selectivity for α -bromo derivative was more in the bromination using dioxane. However the proportion of 3-bromo derivative was comparatively higher, hence the mixtures of both the bromo derivatives was obtained and were separated by column chromatography using EDC-hexane mixture as eluent system. The yields, melting points and spectral data of the various coumarin-4- α -bromo methyl acetate are as follows. **5a^a** yield 91%, m.p. 110–111°; δ_{H} 2.44 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.85 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 5.60 (1H, s, CH), 6.75 (1H, s, C3H), 7.27–7.42 (3H, m, ArH); ν_{max} 1732 (C=O of lactone), 1619 (C=O of ester); **5b^b** yield 93%, m.p. 134°; δ_{H} 2.46 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.84 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 5.58 (1H, s, CH), 6.68 (1H, s, C3H), 7.13–7.17 (1H, d, C6H), 7.20 (1H, s, C8H), 7.53–7.57 (1H, d, C5H); ν_{max} 1741 (C=O of lactone), 1608 (C=O of ester); **5c^{a/b}** yield 61%, m.p. 122°; δ_{H} 2.36 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.38 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.87 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 5.61 (1H, s, CH), 6.70 (1H, s, C3H), 7.31 (1H, s, C8H), 7.40 (1H, d, C5H); ν_{max} 1738 (C=O of lactone), 1605 (C=O of ester); **5d^b** yield 91%, m.p. 154°; δ_{H} 3.84 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 6.19 (1H, s, C3H), 7.01 (1H, s, CH-Br), 7.47–7.51 (1H, d, C9H), 7.61–8.06 (4H, m, ArH), 8.34–8.39 (1H, d, C10H); ν_{max} 1740 (C=O of lactone), 1611 (C=O of ester); **5e^b** yield 84%, m.p. 142°; δ_{H} 3.85 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 5.70 (1H, s, CH-Br), 6.82 (1H, s, C3H), 7.65–7.59 (6H, m, ArH); ν_{max} 1739 (C=O of lactone), 1619 (C=O of ester); **5f^{a/b}** yield 68%, m.p. 128°; δ_{H} 2.40 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.44 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.84 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 5.61 (1H, s, CH), 6.74 (1H, s, C3H), 7.18 (1H, s, C7H), 7.26 (1H, d, C5H); ν_{max} 1725 (C=O of lactone), 1617 (C=O of ester). (^adichloro ethane is used as solvent; ^bdioxane is used as solvent.)

All the bromo derivatives have satisfactory C, H, Br analysis data.

4-(4-Hydroxy imidazole-2-thiol-5'-yl)-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (6) :

Intimate mixture of coumarin-4- α -bromo methyl acetate (1 mmol), thiourea (1.02 mmol) in 5 ml glacial acetic acid was heated to reflux. Reaction mixture was maintained at reflux for 3–4 h. Reaction mixture was now cooled to 30°. Product was isolated by filtration of the solids precipitated, followed by acetic acid wash and then cold water wash. The yields, melting points and spectral analysis of the various 4-(4'-hydroxy imidazole-2-thiol-5-yl)-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (6) are as follows. **6a** yield 64%, m.p. 270–272°; δ_{H} 2.43 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.03 (1H, s, CH), 6.40 (1H, s, C3H), 7.22–7.26 (1H, d, C5H), 7.30 (1H, s, C8H), 7.59–7.63 (1H, d, C6H), 9.18 (1H, s, OH), 9.43 (1H, s, SH); ν_{max} 1705 (C=O of lactone), 2360 (tert amine C=N-), 2700

(SH), 2967 (CH₃ stretching). 3248–3066 (OH); **6b** yield 67%, m.p. 243–245°; **6c** yield 59%, m.p. 292–294°.

4-(2',4'-Dihydroxy imidazole-5'-yl)-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (7) :

Intimate mixture of coumarin-4- α -bromo methyl acetate (1 mmol), urea (1.02 mmol) and Na-acetate (1.02 mmol) in 5 ml glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 8–10 h. Reaction mixture was then cooled to 30°. Product was isolated by filtration of the precipitated solids, followed by acetic acid wash and then cold-water wash. Crude product was then dried in oven and purified from methanol. The yields, melting points and spectral data of the various 4-(2',4'-dihydroxy imidazole-5-yl)-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (**7**) are as follows. **7a** yield 58%, m.p., 159–162°; δ_H 2.20 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.34 (1H, s, CH), 6.3 (1H, s, C3H), 6.68–6.66 (1H, d, C6H), 7.27 (3H, bs, C8H + 2-OH), 7.57–7.75 (1H, d, C5H); ν_{max} 1729 (C=O of lactone), 2360 (tert amine C=N-), 3073–3012 (OH), 2953–2921 (CH₃ stretching); **7b** yield 63%, m.p. 173–175°; **7c** yield 61%, m.p. 200–203°.

4-(1',2',3',4'-Tetrahydrobenzopyrazine-2'-one-3'-yl)-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (8) :

Intimate mixture of coumarin-4- α -bromo methyl acetate (1 mmol), *o*-phenylene diamine (1.05 mmol) in isopropyl alcohol (5 ml) and triethyl amine (2–3 drops) was refluxed for 5–6 h. Reaction mixture was cooled to 20°. Product was filtered, washed with isopropyl alcohol and then with cold water. Solids thus obtained were dried and purified from methanol. The yields, melting points and spectral data of the various dihydro pyrazino derivatives are as follows. **8a** yield 49%, m.p. not melting upto 340°; δ_H 2.44 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.49 (1H, d, CH), 6.68 (1H, s, C3H), 7.16–7.85 (7H, m, ArH), 10.69 (1H, bs, NH), 12.82 (1H, s, NH); ν_{max} 1665 (C=O), 1718 (C=O of lactone), 2360–2340 (tert amine =N-), 3007–2851 (CH₃ stretching); **8b** yield 63%, m.p. shrinks at 285–288°, not melting up to 330°; **8c** yield 54%, m.p. 162–164°.

4-[2',4'-Dihydroxy-5',6',7',8'-tetrahydropyrimido-2-one(4',5'-b)-pyrazine-7-yl]-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (9) :

Mixture of coumarin-4- α -bromo methyl acetate (1 mmol), 5,6-diamino uracil (1.05 mmol) and triethylamine (2–3 drops) in dioxane (5 ml) was heated to reflux. Reaction mixture was maintained at reflux for 5–6 h. Reaction mixture were cooled to 20°. Product was filtered, washed with dioxane and then with cold water. Solids thus obtained were dried and purified from methanol by Soxhlet extraction method. The yields, melting points and spectral data of the dihydro pyrazino derivatives prepared are as follows. **9a** yield 47%, m.p. shrinks and chars at 327–329°; α_H 2.39

(3H, s, CH₃), 3.09 (2H, bs, 2NH), 5.80 (1H, s, CH), 6.57 (1H, s, C3H), 7.10 (1H, d, C6H), 7.24 (1H, s, C8H), 7.55 (1H, d, C5H), 10.50 (1H, bs, NH), 10.81 (1H, bs, NH); ν_{max} 1621 (C=O), 1716 (C=O of lactone), 2360 (C=N-), 3187 (OH), 3400 (NH); **9b** yield 55%, m.p. 318–320°; **9c** yield 59%, m.p. shrinks and chars at 312–315°.

4-(1',2',4'-Triazine-3'-thione-6'-one)-5'-yl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (10) :

Intimate mixture of coumarin-4- α -bromo methyl acetate (1 mmol), thiosemicarbazide (1.05 mmol) in isopropyl alcohol (5 ml) was refluxed for 3–4 h. 3–4 Drops of triethyl amine were now added to this reaction mixture and refluxed for another 4 h. Product precipitated was filtered, washed with isopropyl alcohol and then with cold water. Solids thus obtained were dried and purified from methanol. The yields, melting points and spectral data of different 1,2,4-triazine derivatives are as follows. **10a** yield 65%, m.p. 162–164°; δ_H 2.41 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.12 (1H, d, NH), 5.34 (1H, bs, CH), 6.05 (1H, s, NH), 6.46 (1H, s, C3H), 7.61 (1H, s, C8H), 7.26–7.29 (3H, m, C5H + C6H + NH); ν_{max} 1621 (C=O), 1731 (C=O of lactone), 2360–2340 (C=N-), 3222 (OH), 2923 (CH₃ stretching), 3100 (NH); **10b** yield 51%, m.p. 285–287° **10c** yield 40%, m.p. 178–180°.

4-(5',6',7',8'-Tetrahydro-8-thia-1',2',4',5'-tetrazine-6'-one-7'-yl)-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (11) :

To a mixture of 4-amino-1,2,4-triazin-3-thione (1.02 mmol) in 10 ml ethanol was added (1.02 mmol) dry K₂CO₃ and stirred at reflux for 30 min. The reaction mixture was slowly cooled to 30°. Coumarin-4- α -bromo methyl acetate (1.0 mmol) was added to this mass. Reaction mixture was refluxed for 7–8 h. After completion of the reaction solvent was distilled under reduced pressure. Residual mass was quenched in ice water. Product was extracted in dichloro methane and the organic layer was washed with water. Organic layer was now concentrated under reduced pressure. Crude product was then purified by column chromatography. The yields, melting points and spectral data of various tetrazine derivatives is as follows. **11a** yield 64%, m.p. 149–150°; **11b** yield 59%, m.p. 154–156°; δ_H 2.38 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.40 (1H, s, NH), 4.128 (1H, s, CH), 4.86 (1H, s, CH), 6.68 (1H, s, C3H), 7.34–7.47 (2H, m, C7H + C8H), 7.70 (1H, s, C5H); ν_{max} 1617 (C=O), 1723 (C=O of lactone), 2952 (NH), 3086 (CH₃ stretching), 3223 (OH); **11c** yield 53%, m.p. 158–160°.

4-[1'-(4H)-Benzoxazine-3'-one-2'-yl]-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (12) :

To an ice cold solution of 2-amino phenol (1.02 mmol) in dioxane was added (1.02 mmol) sodium hydride at 0–5°

Note

over 30 min. The temperature of the reaction mixture was slowly raised to 30°, when effervescence ceases. Coumarin-4- α -bromo methyl acetate (1.0 mmol) was added to this mass. Reaction mixture was refluxed for 7–8 h. After completion of the reaction solvent was distilled partially under reduced pressure. Residual mass was quenched in ice water. Product was extracted in dichloro methane and organic layer was washed with water. Organic layer was now concentrated under reduced pressure. Crude product was then purified by column chromatography. The yields, melting points and spectral data of different oxazolidinone derivatives are as follows. **12a** yield 38%, m.p. 220–222°;

δ_{H} 2.47 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.74 (1H, bs, NH), 4.126 (1H, s, NH), 6.75 (1H, s, C3H), 7.12–7.93 (7H, m, ArH); ν_{max} 1623 (C=O), 1723 (C=O of lactone), 2953–2852 (NH), 3378 (CH₃ stretching), 3087–3046 (OH); **12b** yield 43%, m.p. 258–260°.

All the compounds supported with spectral data, have satisfactory C, H, N analysis data.

References

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